

Developing a Fuzzy Mathematical Programming Model for the Allocation and Scheduling of Components in a Flexible Production System

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ABSTRACT: Due to the ever-increasing changes in the surrounding world, flexibility is a solution for pioneering in the field of business. The expansion of the consumer market along with the variety of consumer demands caused these two groups not to function as efficiently as before. Thus, the optimal response to consumer needs became possible only through strategic flexibility. In this regard, one of the basic dimensions is related to a flexible manufacturing system (FMS). The aim of this study is to present a fuzzy mathematical planning model for assigning and scheduling tasks in an FMS. The main objective is to minimize the maximum time to complete the last order (max), the maximum workload of the machines (W_{max}), and the total workload (W), i.e., the total workload of all machines. Since the problem of scheduling flexible workshop manufacturing is an NP-hard problem and obtaining optimal response for medium- and large-size problems is not possible in a reasonable time, innovative or metaheuristic methods should be used. Thus, NSGAI and MOGWO algorithms are used to solve this problem. While the cost of manufacturing and maintenance increased by 3-3.5%, transfer cost increased by 1.8%, which is considered to be unfavorable in terms of cost-effectiveness. Also, the average performance of MOGWO was better than NSGAI.

Keywords: Flexible Manufacturing, Grey Wolf Optimizer, Genetic Algorithm, Optimization

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1. Introduction

Maximizing a company's profit and fully exploiting the limited production resources is a key optimization problem in the strategic planning of companies. Another main issue is the way to optimize the performance (output) of the company's internal production according to the types of products. In today's industrial world, production is viewed as a competitive weapon, and production organizations are placed in an environment whose characteristics include increasing competitive pressures, product diversity, changes in social expectations, and customer expectations. While the products should be of high

quality, they only stay in the market for a short time and should give way to products that are compatible with the latest tastes or needs of customers. Hence, ignoring the customer's request or failing to deliver on time can be very expensive. Also, this has made the issue of information very important for production organizations. On the other hand, the latest surveys indicate that the competitive strategy based on the market is also gradually passing and the strategic perspective of competition will be based on resources in the future. In other words, while companies seek for success by following and making right use of the rules, opportunities, and conditions dictated by the market, the resource-based strategy focuses on a company's unique and reliable advantages and resources, as well as investing to develop and protect them. It should also be noted that the desired production resources not only include capital, land, machines, and equipment but also information, knowledge management, and training. Flexible production is a relatively new policy used by some successful companies to develop and increase competitiveness. This method can help companies to produce all kinds of products according to the customer needs, change production steps effectively, and respond to customer needs quickly. There are different methods to solve optimization problems, some of which find the optimal point of the objective function iteratively and based on the gradient. Although these methods usually have a high speed, they carry the problem of falling into the local optimal trap. On the other hand, there are meta-inventive methods often derived from physical and genetic evolution, which search for the absolute optimal point of the function.

Today, many industrial and service organizations in both the public and private sectors define their activities in the form of flexible production. Given that multiple goals are usually considered in these organizations, the existence of a fuzzy mathematical programming model with the ability to consider different goals can be very useful. Moreover, since industries need a quick solution to the problem of scheduling large-scale production, researchers have tended to use meta-heuristic methods which usually produce solutions close to the optimal one.

Accordingly, the main aim of this study is to develop a mathematical model for the problem of flexible manufacturing systems where some parameters are considered in a fuzzy manner. We also attempted to review the studies conducted in the field of flexible production systems, propose a fuzzy mathematical model to solve small and medium problems, provide a solution method by using meta-heuristic algorithms, evaluate the efficiency of the proposed methods and compare the algorithms, and assess the possibility of using the study model and results for better planning in the existing production systems. This research investigates planning a flexible manufacturing system in a single-period mode. There are different parts in this problem that move by the relevant automatic guided vehicles during manufacturing time. To perform different operations on these parts, certain tools are needed that move between the machines and the automatic guided vehicles. In the research literature, the possibility of moving these parts and tools is called a dynamic machine-tool combination policy. This research had several goals, including minimizing the task completion time, manufacturing cost, and transfer cost.

As these problems are of inexact polynomial types, they cannot be solved in acceptable time periods (Jahromi et al, 2017). Therefore, in order to solve this problem, different metaheuristic methods have been used (Chinyao and Yukling, 2004; Celen and

Djurđjanovic, 2012). Jahed & Tavakkoli Moghaddam (2021) presented a new mathematical model for a production system through a scheduling problem considering a material handling system as an intelligent transportation system by automated guided vehicles (AGVs). The traditional systems cannot respond to the changes and customer demands and for this reason, a flexible production system is used. Therefore, for this purpose, automated transportation systems are used for more flexibility in production. However, determining the best metaheuristic algorithms is a complicated matter. In a simultaneous machine and tool movement policy or dynamic machine-tool combination policy, during the production planning horizon, tools and parts are moved among the machines by guided special vehicles. This policy causes more flexibility in the systems, which reduces the idle time of the machines and the waiting time for the parts to complete the related operations. Thus, it is expected that order completion time can be reduced eventually. This policy was first presented by Jahromi and Tavakoli-Moghaddam in 2012 for the problem of assigning operations to machine-tool combinations and flexible manufacturing systems (FMS). Chan and Swarnkar (2006) presented a zero-one integer linear programming model for the problem of assigning operations to machine-tool with the policy of part movement among the machines; they solved the problem using the Ant Colony Optimization metaheuristic algorithms. They also presented an ideal multi-objective zero-one integer linear programming model for the problem of assigning operations to machine-tool combinations and considered the ideals as fuzzy. The problem was solved using the Ant Colony Optimization metaheuristic algorithms without considering the multi-objective side of the model.

Buyurgan et al (2004) presented an innovative algorithm to solve the problem of assigning operations to machine-tool with the policy of movement among the machines. In this innovative algorithm, the way the tools were chosen for the existing operations was based on the ratio of tool life to tool size for installation on each machine. Chen and Ho (2005) presented a multi-objective approach for solving the problem of manufacturing planning in the FMS environment with regards to four aims, including reducing the total floating time of the parts, load imbalance of the machines, the biggest loading in the machines, and the total cost of machinery. Nagarjuna et al (2006) presented an innovative algorithm based on a multi-stage planning approach to solve the problem of reducing the load imbalance through considering the technological limitations such as time availability of the machines and tool-installing limitations on the machines. Mahdavi et al (2008) presented a multi-objective model for the problem of assigning operations to machine-tool combination in FMS with the policy of part movement during the manufacturing time. Similar to Chan and Swarnkar's model, their model is a zero-one linear programming model with the difference that the model of Chan and Swarnkar is an ideal multi-objective programming while Mahdavi et al presented their model as multi-objective and aimed to find the best pareto optimal frontier.

Jahed, A., & Tavakkoli Moghaddam (2021) also presents a new mathematical model for a production system through a scheduling problem considering a material handling system as an intelligent transportation system by automated guided vehicles (AGVs). The traditional systems cannot respond to the changes and customer's demands and for this reason, a flexible production system is used.

Persi et al (2000) presented an innovative approach in which the stack size is determined in higher stages and the stack size is sequenced in lower stages; also, they are linked to each other through timing. Low et al (2006) presented a multi-objective model to solve the problem of FMS scheduling, in which the average time of floating parts, the average delay of the tasks, and the average idle time of the machines simultaneously decreased. Jahromi et al (2012) used a metaheuristic method called Pareto Ant Colony Optimization to solve the problem of choosing proper tool-machine combinations for order completions; the policy they used was parts movement during the manufacturing period and their objective function was to minimize the total manufacturing cost and time. Flexibility in manufacturing systems is a vast definition and could be of different meanings in divergent fields. Prasad and Jaiswal (2019) reviewed this matter in a study and addressed different definitions for this flexibility such as “the adaptability of the system with uncertainties”, “the ability of a production system to deal with variable situations or instability caused by the environment”, “speed and accessibility of manufacturing units to respond to changes in market phase”, “the ability of the system to quickly adjust any changes to the related factors such as the products, the process, and the frequency of machine breakdowns”; however, they considered “the ability to change or react using lower effort, time, cost, or function” as a more comprehensive notion.

Imaraghi (2005) reviewed the studies related to flexibility and addressed ten types of flexibility: machinery flexibility, material application flexibility, operation flexibility, process flexibility, product flexibility, routing flexibility, volume flexibility (production), expansion flexibility, control program flexibility, and manufacturing flexibility (products). As its name suggests, an FMS has a great flexibility. Generally, an FMS consists of a group of automatic machines which are connected to automatic systems and materials, storage systems, and inventory controlled by an integrated computer system (Grower, 2020). An FMS is a high-level automation system consisting of integrated computer controlling inside the body of multi-objective workstations, storage buffers, and one or more guided automatic vehicle(s). These manufacturing environments have certain features that are required to stay competitive in new markets, including combining a significant productivity rate with a high-level flexibility and effective usage of limited resources. To increase the efficiency in the whole FMS, the manufacturing activities, transport, and storage duties must be scheduled well (Novas and Henning, 2014).

Jahromi et al (2017) reviewed the problem of FMS scheduling with regards to dynamic machine-tool combination policy, which enables the simultaneous movement of parts and tools with special guided devices during the manufacturing time. They presented a zero-one linear mathematical programming model. Also, due to its NP-hard nature, they presented a special evolutionary algorithm. Bouazza et al (2019) presented the problem of dynamic planning for intelligent products in FMS through considering the irrelevant machines, different product families, and different set of operations. Accordingly, the aim of this study is to present a zero-one linear programming model for the problem of FMS scheduling with regards to the simultaneous movement of parts and tools among the machines. Most researchers have evaluated the movement of the part or the tool separately, and their simultaneous movement has not been investigated so far. Hence, in this research, we assume that there is a maintenance system. Also, it is assumed that

some of the parameters are fuzzy and there are several factories involved in the problem. So, we seek to minimize the time to complete the task and reduce the costs of producing and transporting the products. In other articles, the following can be mentioned: Mahboobi et al (2020) reviewed Assessing ergonomic risk factors using combined data envelopment analysis and conventional methods for an auto parts manufacturer. Mohammadi et al (2021) reviewed Investigating the role and impact of using ICT tools on evaluating the performance of service organizations. Taghipour (2023) reviewed A review of the sustainability indicators' application in vehicle routing problem. Asadifard (2023) reviewed A Multi-Objective Mathematical Model for Vehicle Routing Problem Considering the Time Window and Economic and Environmental Objectives Using the Metaheuristic Algorithm Based on Pareto Archive. Taghipour et al (2020) reviewed Evaluating Project Planning and Control System in Multi-project Organizations under Fuzzy Data Approach Considering Resource Constraints(Case Study:Wind Tunnel Construction Project). Khorasani &Taghipour (2020) reviewed The location of industrial complex using combined model of fuzzy multiple criteria decision making (including case study). Hoseinpour et al (2021) reviewed The problem solving of bi-objective hybrid production with the possibility of production outsourcing through Imperialist Algorithm, NSGA-II, GAPSO Hybrid Algorithms.

2. Methods & Model

In this research, given the simultaneous movement of parts and tools, we considered the problem of flexible production systems as a mixed integer programming model. In this system, it is assumed that there is a maintenance policy and some parameters are considered as fuzzy. In addition, it is assumed that there are several factories in the problem, each of which can produce a number of products; also, after producing each product in the factory, it is sent to the product warehouse. In other words, the parts are entered into the production system from the central warehouse. Then, a decision is made as to which factory is better to produce each part. Next, the desired part is transferred to the selected factory, and a decision is made on which machine and operation tool can process the piece. After considering the possibility of equipment failure, the cost and time of maintenance are predicted, which can lead to an increase in the cost of the entire system and the total construction time. After the operation, the part is transferred to the warehouse, but a decision is made regarding which factory each part should be transferred to and from which factory it should be taken out. Finally, the part is transferred to the warehouse considering the cost of transfer. Each piece has several operations that are arranged sequentially and have priority and delay. Figure 1 shows the general outline of the model.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the model

As Figure 1 depicts, the parts are transferred from a central warehouse to the factories and each part is only imported to one factory. Then, after considering the costs and time added to the reason for possible maintenance, a decision is made regarding the desired factory and the operation of making the parts. Finally, the part is taken out of the factory and moved to the warehouse.

Three goals are considered in our model as follows: 1) minimizing the work time, 2) minimizing the cost of construction and maintenance, and 3) minimizing transportation costs. In addition, the assumptions of our non-deterministic model include:

- The parameters of construction cost, maintenance cost, operation cost, and construction time are considered as fuzzy;
- Each piece has different operations, each of which is done with a combination of machines and tools as suggested options;
- The time related to the installation of parts and tools on different machines is considered to be zero;
- There are prerequisite and post-requirement relationships between the operations of each piece or order, so that the operations of each piece must be done in order;
- One tool per unit of time cannot be used simultaneously on two or more machines; in other words, each tool can exist on at most one machine per unit of time;
- Shipping time does not add to the manufacturing time;
- Maintenance time adds to the construction time; and
- Each piece must be made in only one factory.

Index

p
Part
o
Operation
l
Tool
m

Machine
f
Factory

Parameters

$$\widetilde{P}C_{pf}$$

The cost of manufacturing part p in factory f

$$\widetilde{M}C_{pomlf}$$

Operation cost o on part P with machine m with tool l in factory f

$$\widetilde{N}C_{pomlf}$$

Maintenance cost of machine and tool and operation o part p with tool l on machine m in factory f

$$SC_{pof}$$

The cost of transporting part p from warehouse to perform operation o to factory f

$$CF_{pf}$$

The cost of transporting part P from factory f to the final warehouse

$$\lambda_{mf}$$

1 if machine m in factory f needs maintenance and zero otherwise

$$\beta_{mfl}$$

1 if tool l on machine m in factory f needs maintenance and zero otherwise

$$T\lambda_{mf}$$

Maintenance time of machine m in factory f

$$T\beta_{mfl}$$

Tool maintenance time l on machine m in factory f

$$\widetilde{T}_{pomlf}$$

Time to perform operation o on piece p with machine m under tool l in factory f

Decision variables

$$X_{pf}$$

If the manufacturing operation of part p is done in factory f, 1 and otherwise zero

$$Y_{pomlf}$$

1 if operation o of part p is performed using machine m with tool l in factory f and zero otherwise

$$V_{pomlf}$$

If operation o of part p is performed with tool l on machine m in factory f along with maintenance, 1 and zero otherwise.

$$S_{pof}$$

1 if operation o of part p starts in factory f and zero otherwise

$$FF_{pof}$$

1 if operation o of part p is finished in factory f and zero otherwise

$$ST_{pofml}$$

Start time of operation o to perform part p in factory f using machine m and tool l

$$FT_{pofml}$$

Completion time of operation o to perform part p in factory f using machine m and tool l

$$C_{MAX}$$

Construction time

$$(1) \quad MIN Z1 = CMAX$$

The above relationship as the first objective function seeks to minimize the time to complete the work.

(2)

$$MIN Z2 = \sum_p \sum_f \widetilde{P}C_{pof} \cdot X_{pof} + \sum_p \sum_o \sum_m \sum_l \sum_f M\widetilde{C}_{pomlf} \cdot Y_{pomlf} \\ + \sum_p \sum_o \sum_m \sum_l \sum_f N\widetilde{C}_{pomlf} \cdot \lambda_{mf} \cdot V_{pomlf} + \sum_p \sum_o \sum_m \sum_l \sum_f N\widetilde{C}_{pomlf} \cdot \beta_{mfl} \cdot V_{pomlf}$$

The second relationship is the function of the second goal of the problem, which seeks to minimize the cost of construction and maintenance by calculating the cost of production and maintenance if maintenance is needed, as well as the cost of operation. In fact, the cost of operation is a variable cost and the cost of construction is a fixed cost of the factory.

$$(3) \quad \min z3 = \sum_p \sum_o \sum_f SC_{pof} \cdot S_{pof} + \sum_p \sum_o \sum_f CF_{pof} \cdot FF_{pof}$$

The third relationship is a function of the third objective of the problem, which seeks to minimize the cost of transportation, which is divided into two parts: the cost of transporting parts from the origin to the factory and from the factory to the warehouse.

$$(4) \quad CMAX = \max(FT_{pofml}) \forall p, o, f, m, l$$

The relationship of 4 indicators is that the construction completion time is equal to the maximum construction completion time of a part.

$$(5) \quad ST_{pofml} + \widetilde{T}_{pomlf} + \lambda_{mf} \cdot T\lambda_{mf} + \beta_{mfl} \cdot T\beta_{mfl} = ST_{p+1ofml} \forall p, o, f, m, l$$

Relationship 5 indicates the priority and delay of the activities and states that the start time of the next part is equal to the start time of the previous part, the construction time of the previous part, as well as the maintenance time of the machine or tool if maintenance is needed.

$$(6) \quad ST_{pofml} + \widetilde{T}_{pomlf} + \lambda_{mf} \cdot T\lambda_{mf} + \beta_{mfl} \cdot T\beta_{mfl} = FT_{pofml} \forall p, o, f, m, l$$

Relationship 6 indicates the time to complete the construction of a part, taking into account the time of starting the operation of the part, the time of construction, and the time of maintenance and maintenance of the machine and tool.

$$(7) \quad ST_{pofml} + \widetilde{T}_{pomlf} + \lambda_{mf} \cdot T\lambda_{mf} + \beta_{mfl} \cdot T\beta_{mfl} = ST_{po+1fml} \forall p, o, f, m, l$$

Relationship 7 shows the priority and delay in performing operations on a part

$$(8) \quad FT_{pofml} = ST_{p+1ofml} \forall p, o, f, m, l$$

The relationship 8 states that the completion time of one segment will be equal to the start time of the next segment.

$$(9) \quad \sum_f X_{pof} = 1 \forall p$$

The relationship 9 shows that it is possible to make a part in only one factory.

$$(10) Y_{pomlf} \leq X_{pf} \quad \forall p, o, f, m, l$$

The relationship 10 shows that if a part is not selected for production in a factory, it is not possible to select a machine for its operation.

$$(11) \sum_m Y_{pomlf} = 1 \quad \forall p, o, f, l$$

The relationship 11 states that each part can only be done on one machine and it is not possible to do it on several machines.

$$(12) V_{pomlf} \leq Y_{pomlf} \quad \forall p, o, f, m, l$$

The relationship 12 states that if there is no operation on a machine, there is no possibility of maintenance for it.

$$(13) \sum_m V_{pomlf} = 1 \quad \forall p, o, f, l$$

The relationship 13 shows that maintenance is possible only for each operation and each part on a machine

$$(14) S_{pof} \leq X_{pf} \quad \forall p, o, f$$

The relationship 14 shows that if a factory is not selected to produce a part, it is not possible to start the operation of that part in that factory.

$$(15) FF_{pof} \leq X_{pf} \quad \forall p, o, f$$

The relationship 15 shows that if a factory is not selected to produce a part, it is not possible to terminate the operation of that part in that factory.

$$(16) \sum_f S_{pof} = 1 \quad \forall p, o$$

The relation 16 states that it is possible to start any activity in only one factory

$$(17) \sum_f FF_{pof} = 1 \quad \forall p, o$$

The relation states that the termination of each activity is possible only in one factory.

$$(18) ST_{pofml} \leq MX_{pf} \quad \forall p, o, f, m, l$$

The relation 18 shows that the start time of an activity for each part in each plant is calculated if the production of that part is assigned to the plant in question.

$$(19) FF_{pofml} = MX_{pf} \quad \forall p, o, f, m, l$$

The relationship 19 shows that the completion time of an activity for each part in each plant is calculated if the production of that part is assigned to the plant in question.

$$(20) X_{pf} \in \{0,1\}$$

$$(21) Y_{pomlf} \in \{0,1\}$$

$$(22) V_{pomlf} \in \{0,1\}$$

$$(23) S_{pof} \in \{0,1\}$$

$$(24) FF_{pof} \in \{0,1\}$$

Relations 20 to 24 indicate the range of binary variables of the problem.

$$(25) ST_{pofml} \geq 0$$

$$(26) FT_{pofml} \geq 0$$

$$(27) CMAX \geq 0$$

Relations 25 to 27 indicate the interval of integer variables of the problem

3. Defuzzification

Due to the indeterminacy of the model, Jimenez (2007) used defuzzification model. With de-fuzzification, relationships 2, 5, and 6, which have a fuzzy nature, are transformed into the following relationships, respectively:

(28)

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_p \sum_f \frac{PC1_{pf} + 2PC2_{pf} + PC3_{pf}}{4} \cdot X_{pf} + \sum_p \sum_o \sum_m \sum_l \sum_f \frac{MC1_{pf} + 2MC2_{pf} + MC3_{pf}}{4} \cdot Y_{pomlf} \\ & + \sum_p \sum_o \sum_m \sum_l \sum_f \frac{NC1_{pf} + 2NC2_{pf} + NC3_{pf}}{4} \cdot \lambda_{mf} \cdot V_{pomlf} \\ & + \sum_p \sum_o \sum_m \sum_l \sum_f \frac{NC1_{pf} + 2NC2_{pf} + NC3_{pf}}{4} \cdot \beta_{mfl} \cdot V_{pomlf} \end{aligned}$$

$$(29) ST_{pofml} + \frac{T1_{pfmo} + 2T2_{pfmo} + T3_{pfmo}}{4} + \lambda_{mf} \cdot T\lambda_{mf} + \beta_{mfl} + T\beta_{mfl} = ST_{p+1ofml}$$

$$(30) ST_{pofml} + \frac{T1_{pfmo} + 2T2_{pfmo} + T3_{pfmo}}{4} + \lambda_{mf} \cdot T\lambda_{mf} + \beta_{mfl} + T\beta_{mfl} = ST_{p+1ofml}$$

The method of solving the problem and data analysis

To solve the problem, Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) and Multi-Objective Grey Wolf Optimizer (MOGWO) algorithms were used. First, the model was validated and the problem was solved in large dimensions. Then, the solution results of NSGA-II and MOGWO algorithms were compared. Next, parametric sensitivity analysis was performed. Finally, we performed uncertainty analysis and assessed its effect on the

objectives of the problem. All the desired algorithms were implemented in the MATLAB software.

4. Validation of the model

To validate the model, the problem is solved in small dimensions. Then, the results of three objectives (i.e., construction time, maintenance and construction cost, and transportation cost) are considered with increasing dimensions. In other words, it is determined that How increasing in dimensions affected the goals. If the values of the objectives are increased, it can be said that the model is valid. The calculation time is also considered. Table 1 introduces the dimensions of the problem.

Table 1. Dimensions of the problem

Problem	Piece	Operation	Tool	Machine	Factory
1	5	3	1	2	1
2	5	3	1	3	1
3	6	3	1	3	1
4	6	3	2	3	1
5	7	4	2	3	1
6	7	4	2	4	1
7	8	4	2	4	1
8	8	4	2	4	2
9	9	4	2	4	2
10	9	4	2	5	2
11	10	5	2	5	2
12	10	5	3	5	2
13	11	5	3	5	2
14	11	5	3	6	2
15	12	5	3	6	2
16	12	5	3	6	3
17	13	6	3	6	3
18	14	6	3	6	3
19	14	6	4	6	3
20	14	6	4	7	3
21	15	6	4	7	3
22	15	6	4	7	4
23	16	7	4	7	4
24	16	7	5	7	4
25	17	7	5	8	4
26	18	7	5	8	4
27	18	8	5	8	4
28	19	8	5	8	4
29	19	8	5	9	4
30	20	8	5	10	4

Table 2. Validation of the model

Problem	Construction Time	Maintenance Cost	Transportation Cost	Solution Time
1	214	148752	21547	21
2	234	150137	21687	38
3	249	151215	21798	58
4	269	152852	21991	69
5	286	154311	22136	88
6	301	155433	22251	100
7	312	157413	22395	110
8	325	159254	22562	125
9	345	160483	22728	137
10	363	162329	22866	154
11				LOW MEMORY
12				LOW MEMORY
13				LOW MEMORY
14				LOW MEMORY

As Table 1 shows, 30 problems were considered. The dimensions of each problem increased compared to the previous problem, indicating the validity of the model. If the increase in dimensions leads to an increase in the values of the objective functions and calculation time, the validity of the model is approved. The results of this validation are presented in Table 2.

As Table 2 depicts, with an increase in the dimensions of the problem, the values of the objective functions and the calculation time increased. Also, problems 1-10 could be solved using the exact method. However, from problem 11 onwards, we encountered the LOW MEMORY error, indicating that the problem could not be solved using the exact method. Since these are NP-hard problems, meta-heuristic algorithms should be used to solve them.

By increasing the dimensions of the problem from the first to the tenth problems, there was an increase in the calculation time, which indicates the validity of the model. So far, the problems were solved in small dimensions and the results confirmed the validity of the model. As seen, the exact method was able to solve the problems up to specific examples (not all of them). On the other hand, in the real world, scheduling problems are not limited to a small number of parts or machines, and the volume of machines may be more than what is applied in the exact method. Therefore, meta-heuristic algorithms are used to compensate for the shortcomings of exact methods in solving large problems. Table 3 presents the results of solving small-, medium-, and large-size problems using the NSGA-II and MOGWO algorithms.

Table 3. Comparison of exact method and meta-heuristic algorithms in terms of four criteria

Problem	Exact method				NSGA-II				MOGWO			
	The number of Pareto points	scattering criteria	MID index	Solution time (seconds)	The number of Pareto points	scattering criteria	MID index	Solution time (seconds)	The number of Pareto points	scattering criteria	MID index	Solution time (seconds)
1	12	40.67675	0.762732	21	9	41.09543	0.811267	32	11	38.92406	0.68	42
2	10	42.07769	0.753148	38	6	49.0596	0.781056	47	12	42.7857	0.87	49
3	9	56.07379	0.8062	58	9	40.07317	0.80517	58	8	59.12778	0.83	68
4	11	11.72262	0.735135	69	9	19.06003	0.748386	70	11	9.973629	0.75	76
5	16	56.07423	0.76437	88	10	48.05177	0.786143	81	13	40.95506	0.78	92
6	7	42.05845	0.904561	100	10	52.09897	0.874783	102	8	12.14174	0.74	103
7	8	18.98152	0.891556	110	9	25.08553	0.862393	112	10	54.58385	0.80	116
8	5	17.854	89.985	125	11	62.05682	0.834281	135	9	22.65526	0.84	133
9	3	23.245	78.554	137	11	46.09091	0.848825	150	13	33.90457	0.73	149
10	5	24.14825	82.254	154	7	46.05904	0.847949	175	8	56.17748	0.71	161
11					7	38.58047	0.881353	179	11	33.65536	0.73	172
12					12	48.06004	0.9042	190	10	46.0075	0.82	178
13					7	41.0665	0.898588	211	13	29.60076	0.76	186
14					10	48.59033	0.853414	227	14	51.49927	0.67	203
15					9	56.71907	0.875969	252	15	57.69063	0.77	221
16					12	49.9478	0.779495	262	15	39.70712	0.71	243
17					12	51.74392	0.671017	285	10	57.17827	0.76	267
18					11	42.18944	0.819318	300	16	45.51992	0.82	284
19					16	41.19319	0.88473	324	6	43.23898	0.83	311
20					11	54.07759	0.819344	344	11	40.27758	0.81	333
21					6	36.00683	0.846073	355	9	47.35149	0.67	359
22					12	56.7108	0.810771	378	8	43.16729	0.80	372
23					11	48.21727	0.774527	407	8	46.33943	0.73	396
24					12	45.29695	0.87506	429	12	40.19785	0.88	422
25					8	49.13354	0.851545	446	10	60.67836	0.82	440
26					16	46.60002	0.801163	459	11	41.22107	0.72	463
27					10	37.71592	0.713219	478	12	50.72197	0.76	487
28					11	53.18086	0.677046	493	10	45.68458	0.69	510
29					13	36.622	0.749076	514	11	58.42622	0.82	531
30					13	58.96158	0.835031	537	7	37.7584	0.76	546

Figure 2 compares the exact method with meta-heuristic algorithms in terms of producing Pareto points.

Figure 2. Comparison of exact method with meta-heuristic algorithms in terms of producing Pareto points

Figure 2 compares the methods used in problems 1-10 in the form of a Pareto chart. According to the results, the exact method in the fifth problem succeeded in producing the most Pareto points; so, the criterion of Pareto points is based on the maximum. This means that any method that produced the highest points had a better performance. So, it can be

said that the exact method performed better in this regard. However, due to the high fluctuations in the production of Pareto points, the exact method could not be considered as a standard method. Thus, it can be said that the MOGWO algorithm was more successful than the other two methods in producing Pareto points. In terms of the dispersion criterion, which is a method based on the minimums, the MOGWO algorithm created less dispersion and the NSGA-II algorithm created a relatively large dispersion.

Figure 3. Comparison of the exact method with meta-heuristic algorithms in terms of the distance to the ideal point

The distance to the ideal point is another criterion, in which the lowest ones perform better. As the results of Figure 3 show, the MOGWO algorithm produced the shortest distance to the ideal point. So, this algorithm had the best performance compared to the other two methods.

Figure 4. Comparison of exact method and meta-heuristic algorithms in terms of calculation time

As Figure 4 shows, the exact method had the least time, even though there was no significant difference between the three methods in this regard. The exact method had a better performance with a small distance from the meta-heuristic algorithms.

So far, we compared the exact method with meta-heuristic algorithms in solving problems with small dimensions, because the exact method could only solve small problems. In the following, large- and medium-size problems will be solved using the MOGWO and NSGA-II meta-heuristic algorithms. Therefore, from problems 11 to 30, these algorithms are compared in terms of efficiency.

Figure 5. Comparison of meta-heuristic algorithms in terms of producing Pareto points in large and medium problems

As Figure 5 shows, in terms of generating Pareto points, the NSGA-II algorithm generated more Pareto points in large examples. While MOGWO algorithm dominated in medium-size examples, the conditions completely changed in large-size problems. Also, the NSGA-II algorithm created relatively more products in terms of Pareto optimal points.

Figure 6. Comparison of meta-heuristic algorithms in terms of dispersion criteria in large and medium problems

As Figure 6 shows, the MOGWO algorithm had a better situation in terms of dispersion criteria in medium-size problems. However, as the problems became larger, the performance of NSGA-II algorithm improved. Therefore, there was no significant difference between the two algorithms regarding the dispersion criterion.

Figure 7. Comparison of meta-heuristic algorithms in terms of distance to the ideal point in large and medium problems

As Figure 7 shows, regarding the distance to the ideal point, the MOGWO algorithm showed better performance in both medium- and large-size problems because it had a smaller distance to the ideal point.

Figure 8. Comparison of meta-heuristic algorithms in terms of calculation time in large and medium problems

As Figure 8 shows, the performance of MOGWO was better than NSGA-II in medium-size problems. However, there was no significant difference between the two algorithms in large-size problems.

Uncertainty analysis

In the present research model, uncertainty analysis was done according to the value of alpha to show which target was most affected by the increase of uncertainty.

Table 4. Examining the effect of uncertainty on research objectives

Alfa	Construction time	Maintenance cost	Transportation cost	Change rate in construction time	Change rate in Maintenance cost	Transportation cost
0	448	208532	40936			
0.25	450	210404	41135	0.004464	0.008977	0.004861
0.5	454	214258	41498	0.008889	0.018317	0.008825
0.75	461	219966	41981	0.015419	0.026641	0.011639
1	472	227666	42652	0.023861	0.035005	0.015983

As Figure 9 shows, the uncertainty leads to the deterioration of the answer regarding the second objective, i.e., the change in maintenance cost.

Figure 9. Examining the effect of uncertainty on research objectives

Then, the greatest effects on the construction time parameter followed by the transportation cost has been occurred. In fact, with Alpha 1 we see that 3.5% is added to the maintenance cost, which indicates a deterioration of the answer. However, regarding the construction time and transportation cost, this value was 2.5% and 1.5%, respectively. So, the greatest effect of uncertainty was related to the maintenance cost.

5. Conclusion

This research aimed to develop a mathematical model for the problem of flexible production systems. Due to the increase in competitive pressures in various industries, flexible manufacturers try to produce products according to the customer's demand and suitable for the market. Therefore, they can sell their products at better and higher prices to maintain higher profit margins. The competitors that produce in a mass way are more influenced by the market, and it is the market and the customer that impose the price on them. Producing customer-friendly products in a high-tech environment is difficult and may not even sell. In this situation, producers that have adopted a flexible strategy can survive this situation by adopting flexible and timely strategies.

The problem of flexible workshop production scheduling is one of the prominent issues in production planning. The objectives of the problem are to minimize the maximum completion time of the last order (max), the maximum workload of the machines (W_{max}), and the total workload (W), i.e., the total workload of all the machines. The flexible workshop production scheduling problem is one of the NP-hard problems. Therefore, it is not possible to obtain the optimal solution for medium- and large-size problems in a reasonable time, and heuristic and meta-heuristic methods should be used to solve the problem. For this purpose, in this study, two NSGA-II and MOGWO algorithms were used to solve this problem. In the first model, validation was done by solving small-size problems, and the results were obtained from three objectives, namely construction time, maintenance and construction cost, and construction cost. Transport was considered with increased dimensions. After solving the model in small dimensions, the results of the decision variables to determine what the permutations of the scheduling problem are by parts, machines, factories and tools, and the results were presented in the form of a template. In the created pattern, the order and sequence of permutations of the problem is determined and it was determined which machine was assigned to which part in which plant and which tool, and the best sequence of activities was established. Among the criteria that affect the accuracy of shawl performance are the production of the most Pareto points, the shortest distance to the ideal point, and the shortest time. The results showed that the performance of MOGWO was better than NSGA-II in medium-size problems, but there was no significant difference between the two algorithms in large-size problems.

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